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CRYOPRESERVED GENETIC RESOURCES: HELP FOR MANAGING THE GENETIC DIVERSITY OF ANIMAL POPULATIONS ?

ONE FRIDAY AFTERNOON, IN A SMALL TOWN IN FRANCE...

TOM IS ON HIS WAY HOME FROM SCHOOL...

HI MUM,
I'M HOME !

HELLO MY DARLING !
HOW WAS SCHOOL ?

FINALLY !!
TOM IS BACK !

I'LL GO TO MY
ROOM TO DO MY
HOMEWORK !

ALL RIGHT !
AND DON'T FORGET TO PACK YOUR
BAG FOR YOUR TRIP TO YOUR SISTER'S
HOUSE THIS WEEKEND !

A FEW HOURS LATER...

TOM, DINNER IS READY!
LET'S EAT!

AND I HOPE THAT RASCAL
ISN'T CHEWING ON YOUR
SOCKS!

HUH !?!
I DON'T KNOW WHAT
SHE'S TALKING
ABOUT!

AFTER A GOOD NIGHT'S SLEEP...

COME ON, TOM, LET'S GO!
DON'T FORGET YOUR BAG AND
GRAB RASCAL, WE HAVE TO GET
ON THE ROAD...

TOM AND HIS MOTHER SET OUT...

AND THEY ARRIVE AT CHLOE'S HOUSE...

AH, MUM AND TOM ARE HERE.

HELLO MUM,
HOW WAS THE
DRIVE ?

VERY GOOD !
HERE YOU GO, ALL OF TOM'S
THINGS ARE IN THIS BAG.

HI CHLOË !
I CAN'T WAIT TO SHOW ALL
THE ANIMALS TO RASCAL !!!
SEE YOU SOON MOMMY !

MAYBE IN A FEW YEARS, THERE WON'T BE ANY MORE GIRAFFES OR BUTTERFLIES...

BUT... I GUESS AT LEAST THERE WILL STILL BE LOTS OF COWS, SHEEP AND DOGS !

BUT YOU KNOW, DIVERSITY IS ALSO DECREASING IN DOMESTICATED SPECIES.

YOU JUST DON'T NECESSARILY SEE IT !

HUH ! WHAT ?!?

DIVERSITY HAPPENS AT MANY DIFFERENT SCALES !

BETWEEN SPECIES, OR BETWEEN BREEDS, OR EVEN BETWEEN INDIVIDUALS IN THE SAME POPULATION...

REALLY !?!
SO YOU MEAN THAT OUR NEIGHBOR'S
HORSES, TIC AND TAC, ARE GENETICALLY
DIFFERENT ?

HAHA, YES !
THERE ARE DIFFERENCES IN THEIR DNA,
YOU JUST CAN'T SEE THEM WITH YOUR
EYES !

THAT'S WHAT WE CALL
GENETIC DIVERSITY !

EVEN IF THEY HAVE THE
SAME PARENTS ?

WELL, YES !
OTHERWISE YOU AND I
WOULD BE TOTALLY
IDENTICAL...

EWWW !!!
GOOD THING THERE'S GENETIC
DIVERSITY ...

HEY,
I HEARD THAT !

BUT HOW DO WE CONSERVE GENETIC DIVERSITY ?

IT HAS TO BE REGULARLY MONITORED IN DIFFERENT POPULATIONS ! WHETHER IT IS A LOCAL BREED WITH ONLY A FEW ANIMALS OR A LARGE BREED UNDER SELECTION.

IN ANY CASE, OVER TIME GENETIC DIVERSITY TENDS TO ERODE, IT IS INEVITABLE...

BUT WE MUST TRY TO SLOW IT DOWN !

AH...

FOR EXAMPLE, WE CAN MAKE SURE NOT TO BREED TOGETHER CLOSELY RELATED INDIVIDUALS, LIKE A BROTHER AND SISTER...

OTHERWISE WE WOULD INCREASE INBREEDING AND QUICKLY LOSE GENETIC DIVERSITY.

OH, I SEE...

TOO BAD YOU CAN'T STORE DIVERSITY IN A CLOSET AND TAKE IT OUT WHEN YOU NEED IT, LIKE RAIN GEAR...

WELL, ACTUALLY YOU CAN, IN A WAY...

REALLY ?

YES, MANY COUNTRIES HAVE SET UP CRYOBANKS TO PRESERVE THE GENETIC DIVERSITY OF FARMED SPECIES...

AND FRANCE IS ONE OF THEM !

CRYOBANKS ???

CRYOBANKS ARE STRUCTURES THAT ENABLE THE CONSERVATION OF ANIMAL GENETIC RESOURCES.

BUT WHAT'S A GENETIC RESOURCE ?

IT IS REPRODUCTIVE MATERIAL SUCH AS SEMEN, OOCYTES OR EMBRYOS.

THESE RESOURCES ARE STORED AT VERY LOW TEMPERATURES AND CAN BE KEPT FOR A VERY LONG TIME.

REALLY ? LIKE HOW LONG ?

THE RESEARCHERS THEN FOCUSED ON 6 MAMMALIAN SPECIES THAT MAY USE FROZEN SEMEN IN BREEDING PROGRAMS.

SO THEY DOUBLE-CHECKED WHICH BREEDS WERE IN THE CRYOBANK ?

EXACTLY !
THEY LOOKED AT THE NUMBER OF BREEDS AND THE NUMBER OF DONORS WITH SEMEN AVAILABLE IN THE COLLECTION.

AH ! AND THEN WHAT ? WERE ALL OF THE BREEDS IN THE FRENCH NATIONAL CRYOBANK ?

NOT YET !
FOR EXAMPLE, THERE ARE 21 CATTLE BREEDS OUT OF THE 54 OFFICIALLY RECOGNIZED IN FRANCE. FOR SHEEP, OUT OF THE 59 RECOGNIZED BREEDS, 48 ARE ALREADY CRYOPRESERVED.

THEN THEY LOOKED AT THE NUMBER OF DONORS IN EACH BREED ! YOU CAN IMAGINE THAT IF ONE BREED HAS 100 DONORS AND ANOTHER ONLY 2, THEIR POTENTIAL FOR MANAGING GENETIC DIVERSITY WON'T BE THE SAME.

THAT MAKES SENSE ! BUT IT MUST HAVE BEEN SO BORING TO LOOK AT ALL THOSE TABLES WITH THE NUMBERS FOR EACH BREED...

LUCKILY, THEY DIDN'T HAVE TO ! THEY ADAPTED AN INDEX, CALLED THE GINI-SIMPSON INDEX, TO SEE WHICH SPECIES HAD FAIRLY BALANCED NUMBERS OF DONORS PER BREED.

FOR EXAMPLE, FOR DONKEYS, THERE ARE 2 BREEDS IN THE CRYOBANK. ONE HAS 1 DONOR AND THE OTHER 9. SINCE IT IS QUITE UNBALANCED, THE GINI-SIMPSON INDEX WOULD BE CLOSE TO 0.

WHEREAS FOR PIGS, THE NUMBER OF DONORS FOR EACH BREED IS MORE BALANCED, SO THE VALUE OF THE INDEX WOULD TEND TOWARDS 1.

IT'S CALLED THE NUMBER OF EFFECTIVE DONORS !

FOR EACH BREED, IT REVEALS THE NUMBER OF DONORS IN THE COLLECTION, ASSUMING THEY ALL HAD THE SAME NUMBER OF DOSES.

THEN, YOU HAVE TO COMPARE THIS INDEX TO THE NUMBER OF DONORS THAT WERE ACTUALLY CRYOPRESERVED. IF YOU ARE CLOSE TO 100% THEN...

THAT MEANS ALL DONORS HAVE ALMOST THE SAME NUMBER OF DOSES !

YES, THAT'S EXACTLY RIGHT ! EXCELLENT !

SO WHY DO SOME BREEDS HAVE MANY DONORS AND DOSES ?

THAT'S A VERY GOOD QUESTION !

TO TRY TO ANSWER IT, SCIENTISTS USED STATISTICAL ANALYSES !

YUCK !!!

10%

$$y = a + bx$$
$$E(X) \rightarrow 0$$
$$\alpha, \beta, \sigma$$
$$S_e \rightarrow \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$$
$$N(0, 1)$$
$$z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}$$
$$y = f(x)$$
$$S_x = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$$
$$\ln_2(P)$$
$$dof = N - 1$$
$$t_0$$
$$\Phi_j$$

X_i
 D_e
 N

0.05

DON'T MAKE THAT FACE...
I'LL EXPLAIN, YOU'LL UNDERSTAND !

INFORMATION IS AVAILABLE FOR EACH DONOR WITH SEMEN IN THE CRYOBANK.

FOR EXAMPLE,
BIRTH YEAR, SPECIES, BREED AND
THE REASON THE INDIVIDUAL WAS
CHOSEN FOR ENTRY INTO THE
CRYOBANK.

ALL THESE CRITERIA WERE PUT
INTO A STATISTICAL MODEL...

THE OBJECTIF WAS TO LOOK AT
WHICH VARIABLES BEST EXPLAINED
THE NUMBER OF DONORS PER BREED
OR DOSES PER DONOR !

OH RIGHT,
I THINK I UNDERSTAND !
SO WHICH CRITERIA EXPLAIN THE
NUMBER OF DONORS IN THE
COLLECTION ?

WELL, THE NUMBER OF DONORS IS
MAINLY EXPLAINED BY HOW WIDELY A
BREED IS DISTRIBUTED.

NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL
BREEDS HAVE MORE DONORS ON
AVERAGE IN THE COLLECTION
THAN LOCAL BREEDS.

AH OK !!!
WHAT ABOUT THE NUMBER
OF DOSES THEN ?!?

WELL... WE CAN USE GENEALOGICAL INFORMATION, FOR EXAMPLE !

OH YEAH, THE PEDIGREE !

THAT'S IT, WELL DONE ! FIRST, THE RESEARCHERS COMPUTED THE EVOLUTION OF THE GENETIC CONTRIBUTION OF INDIVIDUALS IN THE CRYOBANK OVER TIME FOR A FEW BREEDS.

AND HOW DID THEY CHOOSE THOSE BREEDS ?

WELL, THEY CHOSE ONE BREED UNDER SELECTION AND ONE BREED IN CONSERVATION FOR 3 SPECIES.

THE IDEA WAS TO REPRESENT A DIVERSITY OF SITUATIONS THAT COULD BE ENCOUNTERED IN THE LIVESTOCK SECTOR.

AND THE EVOLUTION OF GENETIC CONTRIBUTIONS IS NOT AT ALL THE SAME DEPENDING ON THE CRYOPRESERVED INDIVIDUALS AND THE TYPE OF BREEDING PROGRAM OF THE BREED.

SO THE IDI WAS CALCULATED FOR ALL COLLECTIONS ?

NO, NOT YET, IT TAKES TIME FOR THE RESEARCHERS BECAUSE THEY HAVE TO GET ALL OF THE PEDIGREE DATA !

DO ALL OF THE BREEDS HAVE GENEALOGICAL INFORMATION AVAILABLE ?

ACTUALLY, THE QUALITY OF THE PEDIGREES DIFFERS QUITE A BIT ACROSS BREEDS.

BUT THEN, DOES THAT MEAN WE CAN'T DO IT ?

NO, WE CAN ! THE IDI CAN ACTUALLY BE ESTIMATED WITH MOLECULAR INFORMATION.

FOR EXAMPLE, BY GENOTYPING THE INDIVIDUALS OF THE CRYOBANK, AS WELL AS CONTEMPORARY MALES AND FEMALES WITH A DNA CHIP.

SO THAT WAY THEY CAN COMPUTE THE SAME THING, BUT IN A DIFFERENT WAY. LIKE A PLAN B !

